

Thermodynamics of Electrolyte Solutions. An EMF Study of Activity Coefficients of NaCl in the Ternary System NaCl+BaCl₂+H₂O at 35 and 45°

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The values of activity coefficients of NaCl in NaCl+BaCl₂+H₂O system at 35 and 45° were determined at the total ionic strengths of 0.5, 1.0, 2.0 and 3.0 mol kg⁻¹ by an e.m.f. method using a sodium ion-selective electrode and Ag/AgCl reference electrode. The data were fitted to the Harned equation and the Harned coefficients (α_{AB}) were evaluated. The data were also analysed using the Pitzer equations and the corresponding binary and ternary interaction parameters were estimated.

ACTIVITY coefficients in multicomponent electrolyte solutions containing NaCl and an alkaline earth chloride are of interest in connection with the chemistry of sea water and several physiological processes. Recently a number of investigators have studied the activity coefficients of NaCl in different 2-1 electrolytes¹ by e.m.f. method and isopiestic method at 25°. However, the activity coefficient data as a function of temperature are still lacking on many electrolyte solutions. Hence, in continuation of our earlier work² at 25°, the present paper reports the determination of the activity coefficient data of NaCl in the system NaCl+BaCl₂+H₂O at 35 and 45°.

Experimental

The cell consisted of a sodium ion-selective electrode (Elico) and a Ag/AgCl electrode immersed in a mixture of aqueous NaCl and BaCl₂ solutions placed in a double-walled glass vessel whose temperature was maintained constant by circulation of thermostated water. The cell arrangement was

Analytical grade NaCl and BaCl₂ (S. Merck, G.R.) were used as such. The stock solutions were standardised volumetrically using AgNO₃. All solutions were added using a weight burette and concentrations were calculated in units of molality.

Results and Discussion

Calculations were done as described by Ananthaswamy and Atkinson³. The potentials of

the Na ion-selective electrode vs Ag/AgCl electrode in NaCl-BaCl₂ mixtures are described by the relations,

$$E_{NaCl-BaCl_2} = E_0 + k \log (a_{Na} a_{Cl} + K a_{Ba}^{1/2} a_{Cl}) \quad (1)$$

where, K is the selectivity coefficient of Na-ion selective electrode for Ba²⁺ ions and k the Nernst slope.

At each ionic strength the e.m.f. values of the cell were first measured with pure NaCl solutions in order to calibrate the electrodes. Then the E_0 and k values were estimated by plotting the cell e.m.f. (E_{NaCl}) against $\log a_{NaCl}$. The values of activity coefficient of pure NaCl solutions at 25° were taken from the NBS data⁴. The values of activity coefficient of pure NaCl at 35 and 45° were taken from literature⁵. The e.m.f. of pure BaCl₂ solutions were then measured to evaluate the selectivity coefficient (K) values. The values of K were in the range 10⁻⁶ - 10⁻⁴ at the ionic strengths studied and hence the $K a_{Ba}^{1/2} a_{Cl}$ term in equation (1) could be neglected. Thus, equation (1) could be written as

$$E_{NaCl-BaCl_2} = E_0 + k \log a_{Na} a_{Cl} \quad (2)$$

On substituting $a_{Na^+} = (m_{Na^+}) (\gamma_{\pm})$ and $a_{Cl^-} = (m_{Cl^-}) (\gamma_{\pm})$ equation (1) could be rearranged as

$$\gamma_{\pm}^2 = (1/m_{Na} m_{Cl}) \exp \{2.303 (E_{NaCl-BaCl_2} - E_0)/k\} \quad (3)$$

where, $\gamma_{\pm}$ is the mean activity coefficient of NaCl in the NaCl-BaCl₂ mixture. Thus the mean activity coefficients ($\gamma_{\pm}$) of NaCl can be obtained by substituting the e.m.f. of the cell with NaCl-BaCl₂ mixtures ($E_{NaCl-BaCl_2}$) in equation (3). All calculations were done on a VAX computer. The activity coefficient data obtained at $I=0.5, 1, 2$ and 3 and at 35 and 45° are given in Table 1 at

TABLE 1 - MEAN ACTIVITY COEFFICIENTS OF NaCl IN NaCl + BaCl₂ + H₂O SYSTEM AT 35 AND 45°

I = 0.5		I = 1		I = 2		I = 3	
y _B	-log γ _±						
35°							
0.092 2	0.168 1	0.093 0	0.184 7	0.095 5	0.171 0	0.098 2	0.146 1
0.168 8	0.169 0	0.170 2	0.183 4	0.174 4	0.174 2	0.178 8	0.150 0
0.233 5	0.170 2	0.235 2	0.184 4	0.240 6	0.175 7	0.246 2	0.152 3
0.288 8	0.171 0	0.290 9	0.187 4	0.297 0	0.175 1	0.303 4	0.156 7
0.336 7	0.172 0	0.338 9	0.184 2	0.345 6	0.176 3	0.352 5	0.158 5
0.378 5	0.172 5	0.380 9	0.182 4	0.387 9	0.174 8	0.395 2	0.157 6
0.448 2	0.173 0	0.417 8	0.181 8	0.425 0	0.174 6	0.432 6	0.162 4
0.477 4	0.173 5	0.450 6	0.182 3	0.458 0	0.175 6	0.465 6	0.163 9
0.497 9	0.174 5	0.462 0	0.184 7	0.478 2	0.177 9	0.467 6	0.162 9
0.503 8	0.174 5	0.479 9	0.183 7	0.487 3	0.177 5	0.493 9	0.162 7
0.553 5	0.178 0	0.485 7	0.180 8	0.504 5	0.180 9	0.495 0	0.162 1
0.586 2	0.176 0	0.506 3	0.186 1	0.513 6	0.180 3	0.521 3	0.165 6
0.623 0	0.177 2	0.512 1	0.183 0	0.533 9	0.181 6	0.523 3	0.164 5
0.712 6	0.176 0	0.541 4	0.182 8	0.567 0	0.183 4	0.556 4	0.167 7
0.767 7	0.182 3	0.574 4	0.187 5	0.604 3	0.185 2	0.594 1	0.166 8
0.832 2	0.179 7	0.611 5	0.188 1	0.647 0	0.185 5	0.637 2	0.173 3
0.908 4	0.180 8	0.653 9	0.183 0	0.696 2	0.185 5	0.687 0	0.171 3
		0.702 5	0.185 2	0.753 4	0.184 3	0.745 4	0.173 2
		0.759 0	0.185 7	0.820 9	0.186 8	0.814 5	0.180 3
		0.825 3	0.184 8	0.901 6	0.188 9	0.897 8	0.185 9
		0.904 3	0.188 9				
45°							
0.090 1	0.165 9	0.091 8	0.181 7	0.102 9	0.170 0	0.104 6	0.142 6
0.165 2	0.165 8	0.168 2	0.184 6	0.186 6	0.173 6	0.189 3	0.146 0
0.228 9	0.163 9	0.232 7	0.181 9	0.246 0	0.172 2	0.259 4	0.148 4
0.283 6	0.163 8	0.287 9	0.181 2	0.314 5	0.177 1	0.318 4	0.149 3
0.331 0	0.165 4	0.335 7	0.182 0	0.364 4	0.176 1	0.368 6	0.152 1
0.372 6	0.168 3	0.377 5	0.184 3	0.407 6	0.176 8	0.412 0	0.152 8
0.409 3	0.168 4	0.414 4	0.183 9	0.445 3	0.178 9	0.449 7	0.154 8
0.441 9	0.165 5	0.447 1	0.184 5	0.478 5	0.178 3	0.454 9	0.153 4
0.471 1	0.163 5	0.476 4	0.182 1	0.490 7	0.179 9	0.481 1	0.155 4
0.497 4	0.166 3	0.490 1	0.183 0	0.507 9	0.178 7	0.483 0	0.158 1
0.499 5	0.165 2	0.502 7	0.184 4	0.520 2	0.180 0	0.510 5	0.155 0
0.525 9	0.167 4	0.516 4	0.181 1	0.553 3	0.181 0	0.511 5	0.155 5
0.555 1	0.167 2	0.545 7	0.180 8	0.591 1	0.181 9	0.512 4	0.156 0
0.587 8	0.163 9	0.578 6	0.181 4	0.634 3	0.181 1	0.543 8	0.155 4
0.624 6	0.164 6	0.615 7	0.181 9	0.684 3	0.183 6	0.581 7	0.159 5
0.666 3	0.167 6	0.657 8	0.180 6	0.743 0	0.184 1	0.625 3	0.161 8
0.768 9	0.167 1	0.706 1	0.182 6	0.812 6	0.186 9	0.676 0	0.163 3
0.833 1	0.163 1	0.762 1	0.182 9	0.896 6	0.185 9	0.735 6	0.162 8
0.908 9	0.165 6	0.827 7	0.181 7			0.806 7	0.168 3
		0.905 8	0.181 6			0.893 0	0.170 1

TABLE 2 - HARNED COEFFICIENTS OF NaCl IN NaCl + BaCl₂ + H₂O SYSTEM AT 35 AND 45°

I	log γ _A ⁰	α _{AB}	RMSD × 10 ³
35°			
0.5	-0.167 1	0.011 4	2.98
1.0	-0.181 0	0.007 1	2.20
2.0	-0.170 9	0.017 8	1.83
3.0	-0.140 9	0.047 0	1.57
45°			
0.5	-0.168 7	-0.006 1	2.05
1.0	-0.181 6	0.001 6	1.39
2.0	-0.169 9	0.018 7	1.08
3.0	-0.138 9	0.034 7	1.14

These γ_± values at each ionic strength were fitted to the Harned equation

$$\log \gamma_{\pm}^{\text{H}} = \log \gamma_{\pm}^{\text{0}} - \alpha_{AB} y_B \quad (4)$$

where, γ_A⁰ is the activity coefficient of pure NaCl at the same ionic strength as the mixture. The log γ_A vs y_B plots are straight lines and α_{AB} values are listed in Table 2.

The activity coefficient data were further analysed using the Pitzer formalism⁶⁻⁹. According to these equations the mean ionic activity coefficients of NaCl and BaCl₂ in pure solutions are given by the equations,

$$\ln \gamma_{NaCl} = f^{\circ} + 2I B_{NaCl} + (3/2) I^2 C^{\circ} NaCl + I^3 B'_{NaCl} \quad (5)$$

different values of y_B, i.e. the ionic strength fraction of BaCl₂, where y_B = 3m_B / (m_A + 3m_B).

$$\ln \gamma_{BaCl_2} = 2f^y + (8I/9) B_{BaCl_2} + (I^2 y_B/3)(1 - y_B/3) B'_{BaCl_2} \\ + (4I^2/9\sqrt{2}) C_{BaCl_2}^* + (I^2 y_B/3)(1 - y_B) \theta'_{NaBa} \quad (7) \\ + (4I^2/9) B'_{BaCl_2} \quad (6) \text{ where, } \theta_{NaBa} = {}^s\theta_{NaBa} + {}^E\theta_{NaBa}$$

$$\text{where, } f^y = -A^* [I^{1/2}/(1 + bI^{1/2}) + (2/b) \\ \ln(1 + bI^{1/2})]$$

$A^* = 0.39849$ at 35° and 0.40620 at 45° , $b = 1.2$ and $\alpha = 2$

$$B_{MX} = \beta_{MX}^{(0)} + \beta_{MX}^{(1)} g(\alpha I^{1/2})$$

$$B'_{MX} = \beta_{MX}^{(1)} g'(\alpha I^{1/2})/I$$

$$g(x) = 2 [1 - (1+x)e^{-x}]/x^2$$

$$g'(x) = -2 [1 - (1+x+0.5x^2)e^{-x}]/x^2$$

The activity coefficient values of pure NaCl and BaCl₂ were fitted to the Pitzer equations (5) and (6) and the corresponding coefficients are as follows:

At 35°

$$\beta_{NaCl}^{(0)} = 0.08192, \quad \beta_{NaCl}^{(1)} = 0.2854, \\ C_{NaCl}^* = 0.000406$$

$$\beta_{BaCl_2}^{(0)} = 0.30048, \quad \beta_{BaCl_2}^{(1)} = 1.233,$$

$$C_{BaCl_2}^* = -0.03344$$

At 45°

$$\beta_{NaCl}^{(0)} = 0.08705, \quad \beta_{NaCl}^{(1)} = 0.2931,$$

$$C_{NaCl}^* = -0.000432$$

$$\beta_{BaCl_2}^{(0)} = 0.3069, \quad \beta_{BaCl_2}^{(1)} = 1.266,$$

$$C_{BaCl_2}^* = -0.03498$$

The activity coefficients of aqueous NaCl in constant ionic strength mixtures of NaCl-BaCl₂ are described by the equation

$$\ln \gamma_{NaCl} = \ln \gamma_{NaCl}^0 - (4/3) I y_B B_{NaCl} \\ + (I y_B/3) B_{BaCl_2} + (I^2/18)(7y_B^2 - 30y_B) C_{NaCl}^* \\ + (I^2 y_B/3\sqrt{2})(1 - y_B/3) C_{BaCl_2}^* \\ + (I y_B/3) \theta_{NaBa} + (I^2 y_B/3)(1 - 2y_B/3) \psi_{NaBaCl_2} \\ + (I^2 y_B/3)(y_B - 4) B'_{NaCl}$$

$$\theta'_{NaBa} = {}^E\theta'_{NaBa}$$

where, ${}^E\theta$ and ${}^E\theta'$ are called higher order electrostatic terms and were calculated as described by Pitzer¹⁰.

The experimental activity coefficient data (Table 1) were fitted to equation (7) to evaluate binary and ternary interaction coefficients ${}^s\theta_{NaBa}$ and ψ_{NaBaCl_2} ; these values are listed in Table 3.

TABLE 3 - ${}^s\theta$ AND ψ VALUES AT 35 AND 45°

I	${}^s\theta$	ψ	RMSD $\times 10^2$	RMSD ($\times 10^2$) with common ${}^s\theta$ and ψ
35°				
0.5	-0.3168	1.0840	2.98	5.63
1.0	0.1836	-0.1510	2.20	2.20
2.0	0.0527	0.0181	1.83	3.00
3.0	0.0417	-0.0020	1.57	3.92
45°				
0.5	0.1482	0.3834	1.91	4.92
1.0	0.2306	-0.1450	1.24	2.14
2.0	0.0823	-0.0005	1.09	4.46
3.0	0.0770	-0.0020	1.14	4.49

Next, the activity coefficient data at all the four ionic strengths were fitted into a single least-square program and common ${}^s\theta$ and ψ values were evaluated: ${}^s\theta = 0.1138$ and $\psi = -0.04206$ at 35° , and 0.1482 and -0.0345 at 45° , respectively

The osmotic coefficient values of the mixtures were calculated using equation (8),

$$\phi = 1 + (2 - y)^{-1} [2f^y + \frac{2}{3} I(1 - y)(3 - y)\{B_{NaCl}^* \\ + 1/3 I(3 - y) C_{NaCl}^*\} + (2Iy/9)(3 - y)\{B_{BaCl_2}^* \\ + I(3 - y) C_{BaCl_2}^*/18^{1/2}\} + (2y/B)(1 - y) I\{\theta_{MN} \\ + I(3 - y) \psi_{MNCl_2}/3\}] \quad (8)$$

where all the terms have their usual significance¹¹. These values are listed in Table 4.

Finally, the excess free energy values of mixing were evaluated using the equation¹²,

$$\Delta G^E = -2.3026 y_1 y_2 RTI^2 (\alpha_{12} + \alpha_{21}) \quad (9)$$

These values are listed in Table 5.

TABLE 4 - OSMOTIC COEFFICIENTS OF THE SYSTEM NaCl + BaCl₂ + H₂O AT 35 AND 45°

y_B	35°				45°			
	$I = 0.5$	$I = 1$	$I = 2$	$I = 3$	$I = 0.5$	$I = 1$	$I = 2$	$I = 3$
1.0	0.826 8	0.838 5	0.886 0	0.940 6	0.824 0	0.835 9	0.884 0	0.938 9
0.9	0.842 7	0.854 8	0.899 8	0.948 9	0.841 3	0.855 0	0.903 5	0.956 4
0.8	0.856 2	0.868 7	0.911 8	0.956 9	0.855 8	0.870 8	0.919 4	0.970 6
0.7	0.867 9	0.880 8	0.922 5	0.965 2	0.868 3	0.884 1	0.932 6	0.982 7
0.6	0.878 3	0.891 5	0.932 5	0.974 0	0.879 1	0.895 6	0.943 9	0.993 6
0.5	0.887 5	0.901 1	0.942 0	0.983 8	0.888 6	0.905 5	0.953 9	1.004 0
0.4	0.895 9	0.909 8	0.951 4	0.994 6	0.897 1	0.914 3	0.962 0	1.014 0
0.3	0.903 6	0.918 0	0.960 7	1.007 0	0.904 7	0.922 1	0.971 1	1.023 0
0.2	0.910 6	0.925 6	0.970 3	1.020 0	0.911 5	0.929 2	0.978 9	1.034 0
0.1	0.917 2	0.932 9	0.980 1	1.035 0	0.917 8	0.935 6	0.986 5	1.045 0
0	0.923 3	0.939 8	0.990 2	1.052 0	0.923 7	0.941 6	0.994 0	1.056 0

TABLE 5 - EXCESS FREE ENERGY VALUES, ΔG^E (J kg⁻¹ OF WATER) OF THE SYSTEM NaCl + BaCl₂ + H₂O AT 35 AND 45°

y_B	35°				45°			
	$I = 0.5$	$I = 1$	$I = 2$	$I = 3$	$I = 0.5$	$I = 1$	$I = 2$	$I = 3$
1.0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.9	0.326 4	13.89	95.66	156.7	3.591	24.6	158.3	443.5
0.8	0.580 3	24.70	170.1	278.6	6.384	43.66	281.5	788.4
0.7	0.761 6	32.42	223.2	365.7	8.379	57.31	359.5	1035
0.6	0.870 4	37.05	255.1	418.0	9.576	65.49	422.3	1183
0.5	0.906 7	38.59	265.7	435.4	9.975	68.22	439.8	1232
0.4	0.870 4	37.05	255.1	418.0	9.576	65.49	422.3	1183
0.3	0.761 6	32.42	223.2	365.7	8.379	57.31	369.5	1035
0.2	0.580 3	24.70	170.1	278.6	6.384	43.66	281.5	788.4
0.1	0.326 4	13.89	95.66	156.7	3.591	24.56	158.3	443.5
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

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